

Clary-Boulee-McDonald Project, Seneca County (41.23139, -83.26845)

Since construction in 2021, the Clary-Boulee-McDonald Project’s primary known nutrient benefit has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing 0.6 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Otherwise, the Project has functioned as a passively managed floodplain of Wolf Creek, though water inputs to this Project were limited due to drought conditions in 2024. These conditions limited opportunity both for nutrient retention and for researchers to assess trends in water quality and relationships between the Project’s pools, as many were dry during sampling visits. Soils do have capacity to sorb phosphate if and when water and nutrient inputs are received to the Project.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has a total of 45 acres restored wetland and is bisected by Wolf Creek, a segment of the Sandusky River. The northern portion of the Project consists of a wetland pool, swale and wet meadow. During high flow, Wolf Creek floods its banks into the swale and Pool 3. The southern portion of the wetland consists of wet meadows and two wetland pools. During high flow, Wolf Creek also floods its banks and flows into the pools via cut banks. During dry periods, Pool 1 rarely holds water while Pool 2 holds water year-round. All three pools additionally receive surface runoff from the surrounding wet meadows. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which Wolf Creek floods its banks and delivers water to the wetland pools.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
45 acres	0.6 lbs	103 ± 70 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar floodplain wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Pool 1 is designed to capture larger storm events from Wolf Creek but primarily receives surface water from the surrounding Project area wet meadow. Lowering the berms between Wolf Creek and Pool 1 could increase the water connectivity between these two features during smaller storm events throughout the year, which could help to increase the nutrient retention potential of Pool 1.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.